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Trigger latency for the sTGC in the New Small Wheel

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1 Summary

The New Small Wheel trigger electronics provides candidate track segments that when extrapolated to the Muon Big Wheel trigger chambers can confirm Big Wheel muon candidates. The matching is done by the New Sector Logic which then sends resulting muon candidates to the ATLAS central trigger. The latency budget for delivering the parameters of the track segments found by the New Small Wheel to the input of the New Sector Logic is 1075 ns from time of the collision at the interaction point. At the end of 2015 the estimated sum of the latency of all electronics components, cables and fibers was 1175 ns. A study was then begun to confirm the latency of all components and to consider alternative schemes that would have less latency. The goal was to reach a best estimate of at most 1025 ns, i.e. to have at least 50 ns contingency. The latency of the fiber connection from the furthest NSW sector to the NSW trigger rack in USA15 was estimated at the time of the NSW TDR as 450 ns, i.e. 90 m at 5 m/ns. It was important to estimate more accurately this latency by finding an actual realistic route for the fibers. A route was found with length of 60 m, i.e. 300 ns latency. (See Section 4, specifically Table 10.) The total latency from interaction point to the input of the Sector Logic is now estimated to be 1016 ns; see Tables 1, 2 and 3. This provides a contingency of 60 ns with respect to the 1075 ns budget. Note that the latency is determined by the path from the furthest Sector.

The latency of the Micromegas was estimated as 882 ns and was therefore not a concern. It will also benefit from the optimized routing of the fibers.

As a consequence, other options to reduce latency, which would either reduce the trigger efficiency and purity or would incur substantial costs, will not be considered at this time. These options are recorded in Appendix A.

Below are presented the latency of the signal processing in the electronics components (Section 2) and of the connecting copper twinax cables (Section 3) and fibers (Section 4). Along with actual *in situ* physical measurements, the Catia 3D Computer Aided Design model of the New Small Wheel was used to find and “virtually” measure some cable and fiber routes.

2 Electronic components

A review committee (Stefan Veneziano, Stefan Haas, Lorne Levinson) met with the designers of each electronics component along the trigger path with the aim of confirming the estimated latency and to find any potential ways to reduce it. The conclusion was that no big gains could be expected without changing the architecture. It was thought that the final merging of Micromegas and sTGC candidates could be 25 ns less than the estimated 50 ns. The merging algorithm will be written and should confirm this expectation. However, the Pad Trigger algorithm is also not yet written and could be longer than the estimated 25 ns.

Tables 1, 2 and 3 show the latency of each component, including the cables and fibers with their latest routing and the shorter time for merging.

The total latency is 1016 ns.

Table 1: Latency of components from interaction point, thru' VMM, padTDS, Pad Trigger

#	Component	Latency	status	Comment
0	TOF from interaction point to NSW ($z=7.9$ m)	26	calc	To inner radius of NSW @ $R=1$ m
1	Pad signal jitter in chamber	5	estim	Worst case due to tracks midway between wires (late signals due to long drift time). Reduced by using 3-out-of-4
2	xmit from pad to VMM	10	calc	worst case distance @ ? ns/m
3	Pad VMM	25	simul	VMM latency: input to ToT rising edge; Peaking Time 25 ns Depends on pulse height, could be as low as 5 ns
4	pad TDS: arrival of last pad to register	6.25	simul	
4.5	TDS pad logic and scrambling	18.75	simul	
4.7	register to serializer	6.25		
5	pad TDS: serializer: parallel input to first bit on twinax	6	simul	
6	cable delay: pTDS to rim	35	estim	Twin-ax cable: @5 ns/m: 0.5 m safety + max of: Large Sector: $\Delta R = 3$ m + $\Delta\phi = 1.1$ m + $\Delta z = 1$ m Small Sector: $\Delta R = 3$ m + $\Delta\phi = (1.7+1.3)$ m + $\Delta z = 0.5$ m
8	FPGA GTX Interface	8.3	estim	2 rxusrclk = 8.4 ns (240 MHz, 4.2 ns period)
9	RX Elastic Buffer	4.2	estim	1 rxusrclk = 4.2 ns
10	RX PMA Latency	23	estim	(for 20-bit words): 110.5 UI = 23 ns (4.8 Gb/s, 208 ps period)
11	Alignment block	4.2	estim	1 rxusrclk = 4.2 ns
11.2	Descrambler block	4.2	estim	1 rxusrclk = 4.2 ns
11.4	Additional latency for 5x20-bit words	21	estim	
12	Pad trigger algorithm	25	estim	8 clocks at 320MHz
12.5	??	3.125	estim	extra clock??
13	cable delay: Pad trigger to on-chamber sTDS	35	estim	See item 6
15	xmit band-id, phi-id, BCID from Pad trigger	20.31	calc	13 bits @ 640 Mb/s DDR

Table 2: Latency of components from Pad Trigger thru' stripTDS and Router to the flexible chains

#	Component	Latency	status	Comment
16	strip TDS: from receive of last bit from Pad trigger to parallel input to TDS logic	6.25	simul	crossing from clock recv'd from Pad Trigger to TDS clock
17	strip TDS logic: from parallel input to parallel output of 1st 30-bit word to serializer	56.25	simul	
17.5	register serializer input	6.25	simul	
18	sTDS serializer latency: 30 bits parallel in to 1st bit out	6	simul	
19	Cable delay: Strip TDS to Router	35	estim	See item 6
21	Reading time of GTP RX	4.17	meas	20 bits: 1 UI *20
22	GTP RX hard core	38.1	meas	20 bits data width, 240 MHz user clock: 3*Tsuserclk + 123 UI
23	Buffer 3*20 bits to find complete 30 bits data packet	12.5	meas	3 240 MHz user clocks
24	Descrambler	6.25	meas	
25	Flexible routing algorithm	12.5	simul	
26	TX scrambler	4.17	meas	240 MHz user clock, 20 bits data width
27	GTP TX hard core	19.5	meas	3×1/240 MHz + 33.7×1/4.8Gb s
28	Fiber: from furthest Router to bracket	58	model	11.6m

Table 3: Latency of fiber from flexible chains to Sector Logic

#	Component	Latency	status	Comment
28.2	Fiber: bottom to top bracket	12.5	model	2.5 m (bottom sectors only)
28.4	Fiber: flexible chains	40	model	8 m
28.6	Fiber: flexible chain to cavern wall	145	model	29 m
28.8	Fiber: cavern wall to 1st rack in USA15	32.5	model	6.5 m
29	Fiber: to 3 racks over	9	meas	1.8 m
30	Trigger processor input deserializer, 1st bit to 20-bit parallel	56.3	meas	GTP-to-GTH, 20-bit word. Measured GTP to GTH at 5.6 G scaled to 4.8 G less GTP TX @4.8 G
31	wait for 100 more bits to complete input data	20.83	calc	at 4.8 G
32	cross from deserializer clock to design clock	3.125	estim	
33	descramble	3.125	simul	
34	alignment of 32 fiber inputs	3.125	estim	
35	distribute data for trigger algorithm	6.25	estim	segment data can arrive on 2 fibers
36	sTGC trigger algorithm	56.25	simul	8 layers done in parallel, measured to be 13 clocks + 5 estimated
37	Merge MM and sTGC segments	50	estim	
38	Re-synch to 320 MHz clock driving output serializer	3.125	estim	
39	Serializer parallel in to 1st bit out to Sector Logic	17.8	estim	GTP at 4.8 G scaled to 6.4 G + 1 320 MHz clock for 8b/10b Sector Logic deserialization and waiting for last bit of msg is not included.
40	Fiber delay: Trigger Proc to Sector Logic 4m	20	estim	5 ns/m
Total				1016

3 Sector cables - copper

This section shows the lengths of the flat copper TwinAx cables which will be used to connect the front-end Electronics with the rim Trigger Electronics and other readout components.

This section is divided in two parts:

1. Information and lengths **inside** sTGC wedge
2. Information and lengths **outside** sTGC wedge

This separation does not necessarily mean physical separation of cables through patch panels, but is done mainly for the purpose of breaking down the path.

3.1 Inside sTGC wedge - FEB to wedge top

Inside the sTGC wedge the routing has minimal potential for change and/or optimization. See Figures 1 and 2, where the sTGC Large Wedge and Small Wedge are shown with their dimensions.

The copper cables run from the inner to the outer radius (left to right in Figures 1 and 2). Their routing is basically straight and non-bending.

3.1.1 Large Wedge

The maximum length traveled on the side of the large wedge is

$$2402 + 272 + 308 = 2982 \text{ mm}$$

Figure 1: NSW sTGC Large Wedge front view. Dimensions in [mm].

The extra length to be added, depending on the box placement, is the length of the large radius edge (right edge in Figure 1) which is 2211 mm.

3.1.2 Small Wedge

The maximum length traveled on the side of the small wedge is 2792 mm. The extra length to be added, depending on the box placement, is the length of the large radius edge (right edge in Figure 2) which is 1732 mm.

Figure 2: NSW sTGC Small Wedge front view. Dimensions in [mm].

3.1.3 On-wedge summary table

See Table 4 for the summary of cables on sTGC wedges.

	Large Wedge	Small Wedge
side routing	2982	2792
extra top side	2211	1732
TOTAL	5193	4524

Table 4: On-wedge lengths of copper TwinAx cables. All in [mm]. For LS, only the side routing will be used, since the boxes are placed in the middle of the large sector. For the SS, the 'total' will be used, and then added to the off-wedge number.

3.2 Outside sTGC wedge - Wedge top to rim box

After seeing the routing lengths inside the sTGC wedge, we move on to the lengths from the corner of the wedge to the rim box. This part is divided in two parts:

1. Large sectors
2. Small sectors

There are two reasons for this division:

1. rim boxes are placed on the large sectors area, due to its being manually accessible during operation of the experiment. Thus, for the small sectors, we have to go a small extra distance.

- the different z-distance that the cables have to travel from the large/small sectors to the JD.

3.2.1 Large sectors

As shown in Figure 3, for large sectors we have to cross larger distance in z , but less in ϕ . It is clear that for the large sectors the top side length (2220 mm) is not extra distance to arrive to the boxes. The estimated distance from the corner of the sTGC wedge to the box is 1876 mm in a straight line. After doing 3D routing, we estimate routing length of $\Delta\phi = 1.1\text{ m}$ and $\Delta z = 1\text{ m}$ for this part. This means a total of 2.1 m for LS.

Important note: Keep in mind that when we take the sums for the large sectors, we should not use the total number as shown in the previous section, but rather just the wedge side routing length, since the routing for the large sectors is symmetric in reference to the boxes position.

Figure 3: NSW Side C simplified 3D drawing. Sectors 6 and 7 are shown with their rim boxes.

3.2.2 Small sectors

As shown in Figure 4, for small sectors we have to cross less distance in z , but more in ϕ . Obviously, for the small sectors the top side length (1732 mm) is a necessary extra distance to arrive to the boxes. The estimated distance from the corner of the sTGC wedge to the box is 1505 mm in a straight line. After 3D routing, we estimate routing length of $\Delta z = 0.5\text{ m}$ and $\Delta\phi = 1.3\text{ m}$ for this part. This means a total of 1.8 m for SS. We will use 2 m for the calculations.

For the small sectors, when the lengths are summarized, the length used will be the one referred to as 'TOTAL' in the previous section, as it is necessary to include in the maximum length the extra distance needed for the far side of the small sector.

Figure 4: NSW Side C simplified 3D drawing. Sectors 6 and 7 are shown with their rim boxes.

3.2.3 Off-wedge summary table

Now we present the summary of the off-wedge sTGC copper cable lengths, as presented in this subsection. These lengths correspond to cables from the farthest corner of the farthest wedge (HO-side) of the respective sector. See Table 5.

The numbers shown will be combined with the on-wedge but in such a manner that the correct table item is used from the in-wedge numbers. See Section 3.3 for the total copper cable lengths.

	Large Wedge	Small Wedge
TOTAL	2.1	2

Table 5: Off-wedge lengths of copper TwinAx cables. All in [m].

3.3 Summary of lengths

This subsection shows the summary of copper cable lengths for large and small wedges. For better understanding, the individual parts are included in the table. See Table 6.

	Large Wedge	Small Wedge
on-wedge	2982	4524
off-wedge	2100	2000
TOTAL	5082	6524

Table 6: On- and off-wedge lengths of copper TwinAx cables. All in [mm].

However, this is just the single cable length. **In the latency tables this will be added three times** in total, since the trigger data goes from the FEB→Rim→FEB→Rim. These numbers are rough but provide a maximum value for the lengths. We note that for the farthest sectors (16 and 2) there is capability to reduce the off-wedge length of the copper cables, by placing the box closer to the SS. This requires a study focused on these sectors and it has not been done yet, ergo the maximum values are considered.

4 Fibers

This section focuses on the fiber lengths, and especially the trigger fibers, which are of interest in the frame of this document.

The lengths will be shown mainly with the help of drawings, obtained from CATIA, a CAD software which is used at CERN for the official drawings.

This section is divided in two parts:

- Information and routing **inside** the NSW
- Information and routing **outside** the NSW

4.1 On-NSW

This part describes the fiber layout inside the NSW. The starting point is the next-to-detector electronics, and the final point is the NSW brackets, which connect to the flexible chains in Sector 9. We break down the scheme as follows:

- The fibers start at the rim electronics boxes. Whatever data arrives there - trigger or otherwise - does so with copper cables. They are described in an earlier section.
- From the rim electronics, for each sector, we have routing of the fibers on the HO-side of the JD.
- When the fibers are next to the brackets, they leave the JD, and enter the brackets
- Then they continue to the flexible chains, after which, the routing is discussed in Section 4.2.

4.1.1 Location and placement of electronics boxes

The current placement of boxes is shown in Figure 5. Boxes are placed on the edge of the JD (rim), IP-side. The Readout and Trigger Electronics should be accessible even during operation, so they are gathered in the odd numbered (Large) sectors.

Figure 5: Position of the rim electronics boxes on the rim of the NSW.

4.1.2 Routing lengths for all sectors

In this section we show the main fiber routing on the JD (Figure 6). The fibers go in from Sector 9 (brackets) and are routed in the inner radius. Every 45° the fibers go out radially to arrive to the boxes. Also the different lengths for each routing section are noted.

See Figure 7 for the lengths from the JD edge to the rim box.

Figure 6: View of the NSW JD with simplified cable envelopes. Note that the view is from HO side, and sectors are removed from the drawing. **RED**: JD no-go areas, due to installation restrictions. **LIGHT GREEN**: JD. **DARK GREEN**: Gas envelopes. **BLUE**: Envelope for main gas, cooling and fiber cables. The sum indicated is the path along this JD envelope only.

One can see in Figure 7, that there is a wide area over the periphery where the boxes can be placed, which does not increase the fiber length. Thanks to this, we make a good assumption for the maximum length on this part, and then we can focus on the main part, on JD, to determine the lengths for each sector. For example, we see here that the boxes for Sector 1 and 2 would be placed in the area of Sector 1 or 2 (in the end they will be in Sector 1 to ensure accessibility).

This means, that in order to determine the different lengths for each sector, the only difference comes from

Figure 7: View of the JD edge, where the fibers go from the JD to the rim boxes in Sector 2.

the JD routed parts, and specifically from the ϕ segments, since the radial path is the same all around the wheel. As we go towards Sector 9, the length of 10.2 m (Figure 6) will range from 10.2 to 5.0 m, which would be the distance for Sectors 8 and 10; the ones with the least distance in ϕ segments.

Going backwards, the distance from JD edge to brackets is similar for all fibers (Figure 7, right).

So one can easily add these numbers to arrive at 11.6 m for the longest routing inside the NSW. After applying contingency factors, we arrive at 12 m, of maximum length of fiber from rim boxes up to NSW brackets. See Table 7 for the various lengths.

Sector	1	2/16	3/15	4/14	5/13	6/12	7/11	8/10	9
brackets to JD	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6
on JD	10.2	10.2	8.5	8.5	7.0	7.0	5.0	5.0	0.0
JD to box	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8
TOTAL	11.6	11.6	9.9	9.9	8.4	8.4	6.4	6.4	1.4

Table 7: In-NSW fiber lengths for Sectors 1-9.

4.2 Off-NSW: from NSW to USA15

This is a crucial part as it represents the biggest length in the route. This section describes the routing of fibers from the end of the NSW flexible chains to the Trigger racks in USA15. This topic is divided in the following steps:

1. Calculate the required cross-section that will leave the flexible chains
2. Define a valid path from the end of the NSW flexible chains to the racks in USA15, that can host the cross-section
3. Specify which rack will be used, and consider extra lengths

4.2.1 Calculation of required cross-section

The cross-section calculation presented at this point has been confirmed by the NSW Steering Group on February 10th 2016, as the baseline estimate for the single-wheel NSW Trigger fibers, after combining into bundles in the patch panel of the flexible chains.

With the help of Figure 8 and 9, we have the count of fibers for a NSW sector. Keep in mind we are interested in the Trigger path, that is the fibers that arrive to the pink boxes.

- For sTGC: There are three bundles of 12 fibers, so 36 fibers. The calculation should include the possibility of not using the Routers (see Appendix A), which would increase the sTGC trigger fibers with a factor of 9/4. So, we assume 81 fibers per sTGC sector.
- For MM: Similar to sTGC, there are three bundles of 12 fibers, so 36 fibers.

From the above, we conclude that we have 117 trigger fibers per NSW sector. Multiplying by 16, we get 1872 fibers per NSW endcap. Multiplying by 2, we get 3744 fibers for the entire NSW system.

The company, FiberNet, has provided the trunk cable options shown in Table 8. We assume that we will use the 144-fiber trunk. This means that the 1872 fibers per NSW, can be bundled in 13 bundles of 144, each with outside diameter 10.8 mm.

Table 8: Various trunk cables: their number of fibers, diameters and efficiency

No. of fibers	Diameter	Area/fiber
12	4.3 mm	1.21
24	5.2 mm	0.89
36	7.0 mm	1.07
48	7.0 mm	0.80
72	8.7 mm	0.83
96	9.4 mm	0.73
144	10.8 mm	0.64

Figure 8: The sTGC fiber plan from a single sTGC sector to the racks in USA15.

Micromegas fibre plan – one sector

Figure 9: The Micromegas fiber plan from a single Micromegas sector to the racks in USA15.

Now that we have the final number of fibers, we have to show the final cross-section. For this, we follow two methods, which both give the same result.

1. Geometrical packing: From Figure 10 we see the realistic optimum packing of 13 cables, which is a circle of diameter 4.24 times the outside diameter of a single cable. This gives us a diameter of $4.24 \times 10.8 \text{ mm} = 45.8 \text{ mm}$, which corresponds to $cross - section = \pi r^2 = 1646 \text{ mm}^2$
2. Packing factor: We use the standard 1.4 factor for cable packing. The total cross-section of the cables is $13 \times \pi r^2 = 13 \times \pi \times (5.4)^2 = 13 \times \pi \times 29.16 = 1190.9 \text{ mm}^2$. By applying a packing factor of 1.4 we get 1667 mm^2 . Transforming this to a circle cross-section: we divide by π and take the square root, to get $r = 23 \text{ mm}$, or equally, $outsidediameter = 46 \text{ mm}$.

These two methods of cross-section calculation agree, and the result is what we will use as a required cross-section for validating that it can indeed be routed through the routes under consideration.

4.2.2 Routing from NSW to wall

End of February 2016, a route was chosen and deemed valid by Sergey Malyukov (ATLAS-TC), Tatiana Klioutchnikova (ATLAS-TC, Design Office), Alexandre Seletskiy (ATLAS Design Office) and Aimilianos Koulouris (ATLAS NSW Services), keeping in mind the above described cross-section.

In Figures 11, 12 and 13, a preview of the route is shown. Note the starting point at NSW Side C flexible chains, and the end point in USA15 racks.

Figure 10: Packing of 13 similar cables. Both ways shown give an optimum packing radius of 4.24 times the single cable radius.

Figure 11: 3D pictures of the proposed route. The green envelope shows the cross section. Starting at the end of the flexible chains and going around the structure, and towards $z=0$.

Figure 12: 3D pictures of the proposed route. The green envelope is the cross section to be routed. Coming out at $z=0$, and following the main cable trays.

Figure 13: 3D pictures of the proposed route. The green envelope shows the cross section. Entering the wall and arriving at USA15 racks.

4.2.3 Routing from cavern wall to racks area in USA15

In this section we show a few details for the path from the holes on the cavern wall, to the Trigger racks in USA15, the length of which is fixed, and included in the route lengths.

In Figure 14 (left) you can see the already existing routing of cables under the floor of USA15, in the rack area and (right) the holes on the cavern wall, as seen from inside the cavern.

Figure 14: LEFT: Under the floor of the first line of racks in USA15. The cables shown here are the ones coming from the holes in the cavern wall. RIGHT: The services holes in the cavern wall.

The main question for this part of the route is "Which rack will be used as end point?". This is not answered yet, but for the total lengths we will assume max distance of three racks away. For each rack an extra 0.6 m is added.

The current MuCTPI, is the second rack on the right series of racks (see Figure 15).

Figure 15: See on the right side the USA15 racks. The one indicated with a red arrow is the CTP. After is the MuCTPI, and other trigger racks.

4.3 Summary - Total length tables

Table 10 shows the lengths of each section as described above, from detector to trigger racks. The main conclusion from this length study is:

The previously estimated total fiber length of 90 m (= 450 ns) has now a maximum value of ≈ 60 m (300 ns).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Upper Sectors									
FEB to box	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056
box to FEB	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056
FEB to box	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056
box to brackets	11600	11600	9900	9900	8400	8400	6400	6400	1400
bottom bracket to top bracket (bottom sectors only)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
brackets to flex.chains	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
flexible chains	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000
flex.chains to cavern wall	29000	29000	29000	29000	29000	29000	29000	29000	29000
wall to 1st rack (USA15)	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500
3 (max) racks away	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800
Total fiber length	56900	56900	55200	55200	53700	53700	51700	51700	46700
TOTAL LENGTH of 5 ns/m cable	72068	76751	70368	75051	68868	73551	66868	71551	61868
Lower Sectors		16	15	14	13	12	11	10	
bottom bracket to top bracket (bottom sectors only)		2500	2500	2500	2500	2500	2500	2500	
TOTAL LENGTH of 5 ns/m cable		79251	72868	77551	71368	76051	69368	74051	
Total fiber length		59400	57700	57700	56200	56200	54200	54200	

Table 9: Total length of copper and fiber cables for the proposed trigger route for all NSW sectors. The maximum fiber length is shown in bold. 5 ns/m is assumed for both fibers and copper cables. All numbers in [mm].

Appendix

A Other options for reducing the latency

The following options are no longer considered since the newly found fiber routing provides the needed reduction in latency. They are recorded here for completeness.

Moving the Pad Trigger from the NSW rim to be on the detectors This would have major impact on detector construction, for example: routing of cables over and between detectors or changes to Front end FE boards if the Pad Trigger is on the detector edges. This option was therefore discarded as not realistic at this late stage of design.

Use only the PAD Trigger to provide candidates for matching The large size of the pad towers would cause unknown damage to the trigger purity and efficiency. Also, the strip trigger logic would likely become non-functional if left unused for several years until Phase 2 when latency is not an issue but the precision pointing of the strips would be required.

Bypassing the Router and instead sending the outputs of all Trigger Data Serializer ASICs to the Trigger Processor This would incur the additional cost of fibers, since nine fibers per sTGC layer would be required, instead of four, resulting in an additional 1,280 fibers. Each Trigger Processor would then need 72 fiber inputs instead of 32. The current prototype cannot handle 72 inputs and a new prototype based on the next generation FPGA would be needed. This option would, however, have no impact on purity/efficiency or detectors and Front end boards.

Air core fibers This would reduce the latency of the fibers by a ratio of 5 ns/m to 3.3 ns/m. However such fibers are very expensive and each end must be bonded by hand to a solid core fiber for coupling to connectors.

B Alternative fiber routes

B.1 Routing from NSW to wall

In this section we show two alternative routes, one of which is considered valid to route the required fiber cross-section.

Beginning of January 2016 the NSW requested and received a route, drawn up by Sergey Malyukov and Alexandre Seletskiy. During validation of this route (Route A), another route was found by Agostino Lanza and Aimilianos Koulouris (Route B).

These two paths will now be described.

B.1.1 Route A

In Figure 16, a partial preview of the cavern is shown. Note the starting point at NSW Side C, and the end point in USA15 racks. Both will be looked at closely in the next pictures.

Figure 16: Partial preview of the ATLAS cavern. **Left:** NSW Side C, and part of the Barrel Toroid (in Sector 8). **Middle:** the wall between the experiment and USA15. **Right:** the racks at USA15.

Zooming in the NSW, the starting point of the route can be seen, at the top of the upper bracket of the NSW, in Sector 9. See Figures 17 and 18.

Note that the route shown in the 3D drawings bypasses the NSW flexible chains. As it will be described later, the flexible chains can eventually be included in the route, costing an extra 8 m in cable length.

Figure 17: Close-up of the NSW Sector 9 upper bracket (Point of view from HO). The starting point of the route can be seen. See next image for a better close-up.

Figure 18: Close-up of the NSW Sector 9 upper bracket. The starting point of the route can be seen. See previous image for a wider view.

Figure 19: Close-up of the NSW Sector 9 upper bracket (Point of view from HS). The starting point of the route can be seen. Also the first segments of the route can be seen, namely on the Barrel Toroid.

Next, in Figure 19, the first segment of routing is shown. From the top NSW bracket, the path goes directly upwards and on the Barrel Toroid. After, it follows a service plate, which can be seen in Figure 20. This service plate continues in the z-direction, and the route follows until $z=0$.

Figure 20: Photo from the starting point of the route. The metallic plate in the center is the service plate which would serve as support for the routed material.

At $z=0$, the route turns 90 degrees towards HS and USA15, and goes straight to the wall (Figures 21 and 22). In reality this segment would follow the main cable trays already in place, and, if required, new tray could be installed.

The route, having arrived at the cavern wall, enters the cable/service holes of the wall, and arrives at the rack area of USA15. This part is equivalent for both routes, and will be described in the next subsection. We will now continue to Route B.

Figure 21: Wide view of the route leaving the Barrel Toroid, and going towards the cavern wall. Point of view from HS.

Figure 22: Wide view of the route leaving the Barrel Toroid, and going towards the cavern wall. Point of view from HO.

Note: The presented route A is a simplified version and is supported by confirmation from Technical Coordination (Sergey Malyukov) as being the shortest route from the NSW to the Trigger racks of USA15. The term "simplified" is used because, at the time this document was written, there are no studies/comments included for:

- cross-section suitability
- installation difficulties

B.1.2 Route B

This route follows a path similar to Route A. However it differs in two important points:

- The foreseen routing offers much easier installation. As you will see, it is manually accessible through the majority of its length, even without opening of the NSW or some other component.
- The pre-existing cable trays to be used have more than enough space to accommodate the required cross-section.

In the next 3D drawings we will show the segments of this path. In parallel there will be actual photos from the locations shown in the 3D, in order to allow better understanding for the reader.

Moreover, in the live photos, we included a dummy cross-section, which corresponds to the previously calculated outside diameter of 46 mm. To emulate this cross-section we took a paper poster, rolled it, and placed it in the various locations. As can be seen from the pictures, in most places it fits easily, and even allows for deviation from the initially calculated cross-section. See Figure 23 for the dummy cross-section dimensions. The outside diameter is 50 mm.

Figure 23: The poster we used as a test cross-section to show that the proposed route is valid and respects spatial constraints.

In the next series of pictures (Figures 24 . . . 38) you will see 3D drawings along with their live photos. In the live photos the poster is shown in the foreseen routing position. In the 3D drawings there are markers to show the position of the poster as shown in the live photo. Also, there are arrows to show the point of

view from which the live photo was taken. Follow the captions for descriptions. Note that the 8 m of the flexible chains are also an extra segment to be added in the summary tables in the next section.

Figure 24: The start point of the new route: The end of the upper flexible chains of the NSW. First segment goes towards the floor attaching the cross-section on the general experiment structure. There is space there around the main piece, where already there are other bundles routed. For the case that this particular segment is not acceptable for some reason, there is a certain backup following the current SW fibers, which leads to an extra 2 m. However the space there looks very usable.

Figure 25: After going towards the floor with the previous segment, we move in z and then down again. This part is also foreseen to attach on the structure, where there is a lot of free space. Other not visible potential cable trays would also work, but there is no issue visible with taking up that space.

Figure 26: After moving towards the floor in the previous segment, the routing continues outwards radially, on the Barrel Toroid structure. There are a couple cables already routed on that part of the Barrel Toroid, and space is abundant.

Figure 27: View of the lastly described segment, looking outwards radially. Also visible in this photo is the main cable tray which would house the fibers for routing along z .

Figure 28: As described in the previous segment, now the view shows the main cable tray, which is practically empty. This tray goes from the NSW z , to $z=0$. The contents of this tray are as seen in the photo for its entire length, in both Side C and A.

Figure 29: From the same standpoint as the previous figure, now looking towards $z=0$.

Figure 30: Still in $z=0$, as in the previous figure. Now the photo shows where the fibers would be routed to go upwards, towards the main z_0 trays, which lie on the LAr flexible chains. Again, there are some cavities in the structure to add cables, and there is also space to possibly add extra service trays.

Figure 31: Still in $z=0$. Now the viewer is standing up, looking towards HS/USA15. See the next figure which includes the cross-section.

Figure 32: Still in $z=0$. Now the viewer is standing up, looking towards HS/USA15. This next figure includes the cross-section, which again looks to be able to fit easily in the available space.

Figure 33: Still in $z=0$. Now the viewer is on top of the strut, looking at the cable trays which were in the view in the last two figures.

Figure 34: The previous view from a different angle, looking towards HS/USA15.

Figure 35: View similar to the last. Slowly bringing the cross-section above the LAr flexible chains, and out of the Toroid area.

Figure 36: View similar to the previous one. Viewer is standing and poster is placed.

Figure 37: View similar to the previous one. Now viewer is out of the Toroid area, and looking towards the beam pipe.

Figure 38: The final segments are on the cable trays above the LAr flexible chains, at $z=0$. There is a lot of space there, either to route the cables, or to add new service trays. The description ends, as in the previous route, at the holes in the wall.

B.2 Total length tables

The total lengths of the alternative cavern routes are presented in Table 10 below.

Sector	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
FEB to box	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056
box to FEB	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056
FEB to box	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056	6617	5056
box to brackets	11600	11600	9900	9900	8400	8400	6400	6400	1400
bottom bracket to top bracket (bottom sectors only)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
brackets to flex.chains	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
flexible chains	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000
flex.chains to cavern wall - Route A	28000	28000	28000	28000	28000	28000	28000	28000	28000
flex.chains to cavern wall - Route B	30000	30000	30000	30000	30000	30000	30000	30000	30000
wall to 1st rack (USA15)	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500
3 (max) racks away	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800	1800
Total fiber length - Route A	55900	55900	54200	54200	52700	52700	50700	50700	45700
Total fiber length - Route B	57900	57900	56200	56200	54700	54700	52700	52700	47700
TOTAL LENGTH of 5ns/m cable - Route A	71068	75751	69368	74051	67868	72551	65868	70551	60868
TOTAL LENGTH of 5ns/m cable - Route B	73068	77751	71368	76051	69868	74551	67868	72551	62868
Sector		16	15	14	13	12	11	10	
bottom bracket to top bracket (bottom sectors only)		2500	2500	2500	2500	2500	2500	2500	
TOTAL LENGTH of 5ns/m cable - Route A		78251	71868	76551	70368	75051	68368	73051	
TOTAL LENGTH of 5ns/m cable - Route B		80251	73868	78551	72368	77051	70368	75051	
Total fiber length - Route A		58400	56700	56700	55200	55200	53200	53200	
Total fiber length - Route B		60400	58700	58700	57200	57200	55200	55200	

Table 10: Total lengths of copper and fiber cables for the trigger routes A and B for all NSW sectors. 5 ns/m is assumed for both fibers and copper cables. All numbers in [mm].

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